

Supplementary econometric appendix: Remittances and migration between Mexico and the United States

Appendix A Series Used

Note: Authors' calculations based on data from BANXICO (2025), INEGI (2025), FRED (2025), U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (2025) y U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2025).

Appendix B Unit Root Tests

Variable	Deterministic	ADF stat	CV(5 %)	ADF Decision	PP stat	PP Decision	KPSS stat	KPSS Decision	Conclusion
Levels									
remr_s	No constant	1.246	-1.95	Fail to reject UR	-20.639	Reject UR	3.691	Reject stationarity	Non-stationary
	Constant	-1.339	-2.88	Fail to reject UR	-20.639	Reject UR	3.691	Reject stationarity	
	Const. + trend	-2.148	-3.43	Fail to reject UR	-20.639	Reject UR	0.367	Reject stationarity	
pib_usa_s	No constant	0.670	-1.95	Fail to reject UR	-18.69	Fail to reject UR	1.632	Reject stationarity	Non-stationary
	Constant	-2.978	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.05)	-18.69	Fail to reject UR	1.632	Reject stationarity	
	Const. + trend	-3.247	-3.43	Reject UR (p<0.10)	-18.69	Fail to reject UR	0.336	Reject stationarity	
pib_mx_s	No constant	1.418	-1.95	Fail to reject UR	-36.22	Reject UR	2.935	Reject stationarity	Non-stationary
	Constant	-1.989	-2.88	Fail to reject UR	-36.22	Reject UR	2.935	Reject stationarity	
	Const. + trend	-3.890	-3.43	Reject UR (p<0.05)	-36.22	Reject UR	0.329	Reject stationarity	
trc_s	No constant	0.439	-1.95	Fail to reject UR	-6.15	Fail to reject UR	2.211	Reject stationarity	Non-stationary
	No constant	-1.989	-2.88	Fail to reject UR	-6.15	Fail to reject UR	2.211	Reject stationarity	
	No constant	-1.861	-3.43	Fail to reject UR	-6.15	Fail to reject UR	0.633	Reject stationarity	
ice_d_s	No constant	-0.070	-1.95	Fail to reject UR	-19.14	Reject UR	1.061	Reject stationarity	Non-stationary
	Constant	-2.813	-2.88	Fail to reject UR	-19.14	Reject UR	1.061	Reject stationarity	
	Const. + trend	-3.154	-3.43	Fail to reject UR	-19.14	Reject UR	0.100	Reject stationarity	
cbp_e_s	No constant	-0.554	-1.95	Fail to reject UR	-5.87	Fail to reject UR	1.279	Reject stationarity	Non-stationary
	Constant	-2.155	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.05)	-5.87	Fail to reject UR	1.279	Reject stationarity	
	Const. + trend	-1.818	-3.43	Reject UR (p<0.10)	-5.87	Fail to reject UR	0.206	Reject stationarity	
First Differences (Δ)									
Δremr_s	No constant	-11.067	-1.95	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-233.56	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.058	Fail to reject stationarity	Stationary
	Constant	-8.126	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-233.56	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.058	Fail to reject stationarity	
Δpib_usa_s	No constant	-11.473	-1.95	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-123.76	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.116	Fail to reject stationarity	Stationary
	Constant	-11.475	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-123.76	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.116	Fail to reject stationarity	
Δpib_mx_s	No constant	-9.039	-1.95	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-175.12	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.035	Fail to reject stationarity	Stationary
	Constant	-7.258	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-175.12	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.035	Fail to reject stationarity	
Δtrc_s	No constant	-9.171	-1.95	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-129.58	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.111	Fail to reject stationarity	Stationary
	Constant	-9.170	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-129.58	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.111	Fail to reject stationarity	
Δice_d_s	No constant	-8.151	-1.95	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-153.65	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.039	Fail to reject stationarity	Stationary
	Constant	-8.128	-2.88	Reject UR (p<0.01)	-153.65	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.039	Fail to reject stationarity	
Δcbp_e_s	No constant	-2.494	-1.95	Reject UR (p<0.05)	-118.21	Reject UR (p<0.01)	0.196	Fail to reject stationarity	Stationary
	Constant	-2.495	-88	Fail to reject UR	118.21	Reject UR (p<0.01)	.196	Fail to reject stationarity	

Note: Authors' calculations based on BM (2025), INEGI (2025), FRED (2025), U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (2025) y U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2025)

At levels, the dominant pattern is non-stationarity: the ADF test fails to reject the unit root in most specifications, the PP test rejects in some cases, and the KPSS test generally rejects stationarity. In first differences, both ADF and PP reject the unit root null, and KPSS fails to reject stationarity for all variables in at least one specification. Under a strict 5% significance criterion, all series are concluded to be integrated of order one, I(1).

Appendix C

Trace Test

Deterministic Specification	r_0	Trace Statistic	CV 10%	Decision 10%	CV 5%	Decision 5%
none	0	0.457	6.5	Do not reject H_0	8.18	Do not reject H_0
none	1	5.133	15.66	Do not reject H_0	17.95	Do not reject H_0
none	2	13.682	28.71	Do not reject H_0	31.52	Do not reject H_0
none	3	28.321	45.23	Do not reject H_0	48.28	Do not reject H_0
none	4	52.094	66.49	Do not reject H_0	70.6	Do not reject H_0
none	5	127.803	85.18	Do not reject H_0	90.39	Do not reject H_0
const	0	3.874	7.52	Do not reject H_0	9.24	Do not reject H_0
const	1	9.735	17.85	Do not reject H_0	19.96	Do not reject H_0
const	2	18.366	32	Do not reject H_0	34.91	Do not reject H_0
const	3	35.076	49.65	Do not reject H_0	53.12	Do not reject H_0
const	4	59.207	71.86	Do not reject H_0	76.07	Do not reject H_0
const	5	150.131	97.18	Do not reject H_0	102.14	Do not reject H_0
trend	0	4.179	10.49	Do not reject H_0	12.25	Do not reject H_0
trend	1	10.807	22.76	Do not reject H_0	25.32	Do not reject H_0
trend	2	25.173	39.06	Do not reject H_0	42.44	Do not reject H_0
trend	3	44.346	59.14	Do not reject H_0	62.99	Do not reject H_0
trend	4	74.929	83.2	Do not reject H_0	87.31	Do not reject H_0
trend	5	161.866	110.42	Do not reject H_0	114.9	Do not reject H_0

Note: Authors' calculations based on BM (2025), INEGI (2025), FRED (2025), U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (2025) y U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2025).

Appendix D

Maximum Eigenvalue Test

Deterministic Specification	r_0	Trace Statistic	CV 10%	Decision 10%	CV 5%	Decision 5%
none	0	0.457	6.5	Do not reject H_0	8.18	Do not reject H_0
none	1	4.677	12.91	Do not reject H_0	14.9	Do not reject H_0
none	2	8.549	18.9	Do not reject H_0	21.07	Do not reject H_0
none	3	14.638	24.78	Do not reject H_0	27.14	Do not reject H_0
none	4	23.774	30.84	Do not reject H_0	33.32	Do not reject H_0
none	5	75.708	36.25	Do not reject H_0	39.43	Do not reject H_0
const	0	3.874	7.52	Do not reject H_0	9.24	Do not reject H_0
const	1	5.861	13.75	Do not reject H_0	15.67	Do not reject H_0
const	2	8.631	19.77	Do not reject H_0	22	Do not reject H_0
const	3	16.711	25.56	Do not reject H_0	28.14	Do not reject H_0
const	4	24.130	31.66	Do not reject H_0	34.4	Do not reject H_0
const	5	90.924	37.45	Do not reject H_0	40.3	Do not reject H_0
trend	0	4.179	10.49	Do not reject H_0	12.25	Do not reject H_0
trend	1	6.628	16.85	Do not reject H_0	18.96	Do not reject H_0
trend	2	14.366	23.11	Do not reject H_0	25.54	Do not reject H_0
trend	3	19.173	29.12	Do not reject H_0	31.46	Do not reject H_0
trend	4	30.583	34.75	Do not reject H_0	37.52	Do not reject H_0
trend	5	86.937	40.91	Do not reject H_0	43.97	Do not reject H_0

Note: Authors' calculations based on (2025), INEGI (2025), FRED (2025), U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (2025) y U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2025).

Appendix E

Rank Summary

Deterministic	r (10%) trace	r (10%) max-eig	r (5%) trace	r (5%) max-eig
none	0	0	0	0
const	0	0	0	0
trend	0	0	0	0

Note: Authors' calculations based on BM (2025), INEGI (2025), FRED (2025), U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (2025) y U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2025).

The Johansen (1995) tests applied under the three standard deterministic specifications (none, constant, and trend) clearly indicate that neither the trace nor the maximum eigenvalue statistics exceed the corresponding critical values at the 10% or 5% significance levels for any rank. The estimated cointegration rank is $r = 0$ in all cases, ruling out the existence of long-run equilibrium relationships among remittances, U.S. and Mexican economic activity, the real exchange rate, ICE, and CBP. Accordingly, the system does not exhibit a shared long-run equilibrium, and the analysis proceeds coherently under a VAR specification in levels focused on short- and medium-term dynamics and transitory shock effects.

Appendix F

Lag Length Selection Criteria (p)

p	AIC(n)	HQ(n)	SC(n)	FPE(n)
1	-39.08249	-38.69105	-38.11723*	1.06E-17
2	-39.63996	-38.98756	-38.03119	6.10E-18
3	-39.96772	-39.05436*	-37.71544	4.4169e-18*
4	-39.81377	-38.63945	-36.91799	5.19E-18
5	-39.66885	-38.23357	-36.12956	6.07E-18
6	-39.74476	-38.04853	-35.56197	5.73E-18
7	-39.61695	-37.65975	-34.79065	6.66E-18
8	-39.63439	-37.41624	-34.16459	6.76E-18
9	-39.59701	-37.11789	-33.48369	7.31E-18
10	-39.59583	-36.85576	-32.83901	7.71E-18
11	-39.89591	-36.89488	-32.49558	6.09E-18
12	-37.76682	-34.57926	-29.9072	5.42E-17

Note: An asterisk indicates the optimal lag length suggested by each information criterion. Authors' calculations based on BM (2025), INEGI (2025), FRED (2025), U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (2025) y U.S. Department of Homeland Security (2025).

Information criteria were employed to determine the optimal lag length of the VAR estimated in levels. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and the Final Prediction Error (FPE), both characterized by relatively lenient penalties on model complexity, reach their minima at twelve and three lags, respectively. In particular, the FPE suggests $p = 3$ as the most efficient specification in predictive terms, whereas the AIC continues declining up to $p = 12$, reflecting its tendency to favour more heavily parameterized multivariate systems. The Hannan–Quinn (HQ) criterion, which imposes an intermediate penalty, also indicates a local

minimum at three lags, while the Schwarz Criterion (SC), the most restrictive, favours a single lag. In this context, selecting a three-lag specification is methodologically appropriate, as it coincides with the minima of both the FPE and HQ criteria.